

ISic3499

I.Sicily inscription 3499

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list

Material

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336192

1. Εἶσ [— — — — —]

2. Εὐτύ [χης(?) — —]

3. Αἶδο [— — — — —]

4. [— — — — — — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645367

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1331.5

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 68 no.61 fig.143

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